

Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds (Reksa Dana): Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Mutual Funds " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics regarding Mutual Funds based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that there are 522 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Mutual Funds, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Mutual Funds; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Mutual funds in general are funds collected from various investors with different amounts. These funds are then managed by an investment manager and invested in various instruments such as securities, sukuk, Bank Indonesia Certificates (SBI), deposits, etc.(Arifin, 2017).

Sharia mutual funds are different from conventional mutual funds which can be seen from the use of funds collected, the selection of securities and assets to form the portfolio. Sharia mutual funds are not allowed to use funds for things that are prohibited in Islam, such as bank interest, khamr, casino games, cigarettes, and things that contain pork. (Rahayu, 2019).

The Indonesian government established PT Danareksa in 1976. The government also issued capital market regulations in 1995, namely PP Number 8 of 1995 concerning Capital Markets, which also regulates mutual funds. PT Danareksa Investment established sharia mutual funds on July 3 1997 (Johari, 2018).

Research on mutual funds develops every year. According to data from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), 218 research documents on mutual funds have been found from 1998 to 2022. However, bibliometric-based research on mutual funds has not been found.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding mutual fund use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Mutual Funds, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The

implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Mutual Funds, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Conventional Mutual Funds are public funds that can be collected and reinvested in securities portfolios by Investment Managers. Sharia Mutual Funds are joint assets that are run in accordance with Islamic legal regulations and standards, both as an agreement between the financial backer as the property owner (shahib al-mal/Rabb al Mal) and the Investment Manager as the shahib al-mal delegate, as well as between the venture supervisor as shahib al-mal agents and Investment clients. This definition is based on the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) No. 20/DSN-MUI/IV/2001 concerning Business Implementation Rules for Sharia Mutual Funds..

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications (Dubyna et al., 2022) .

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-

understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology (van Eck NJ, 2022) .

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The research object is Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Mutual Funds originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Mutual Funds ", "Mutual Funds" and "Mutual Funds" for the entire year (2010-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research (Budianto, 2022) .

Results and Discussion

In this chapter, we will discuss the mapping of Mutual Fund research in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions based on VOSviewer bibliometric studies and Library Research studies.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds

Search results via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) regarding Mutual Funds in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions from 1998 to 2022 resulted in 200 titles of scientific publications being published. In 2019, there were the highest number of scientific publications published, namely 27 articles. So, on average every year there are 8 scientific articles published on the theme of Mutual Funds in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Tab el 1. Scientific publication data regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
1998	1	2010	4	2017	21
2003	2	2011	3	2018	18
2004	1	2012	4	2019	27
2005	2	2013	11	2020	20
2007	2	2014	19	2021	17
2008	2	2015	3	2022	23
2009	3	2016	16		
Total 199					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 20 16.

In table 2, there are 7 affiliates/institutions that publish the most scientific articles about Mutual Funds in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. Diponegoro Journal of Management from Brawijaya University is the institution that publishes the most journals with a total of 9 articles published.

Tab el 2. Affiliate/institution publishing journals regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Diponegoro Journal of Management, Diponegoro University	9
FEB Student Scientific Journal, Brawijaya University	8
Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, Airlangga University	6
E-Journal of Accounting, Udayana University	4
Finesta, Christian Petra University, Journal of Applied Islamic Economics and Finance, Bandung State Polytechnic, Gaussian Journal, Diponegoro University	3

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 20 16.

Meanwhile, in table 3, the researcher who has written the most scientific journals about Mutual Funds in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions is Imron Mawardi from Airlangga University with a total of 3 articles published.

Tab el 3. Researcher productivity regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds

Researcher	Number of Publications
Imron Mawardi (Airlangga University)	3
Cahyaningsih (Sebelas Maret University), Waelan (Indonesian Islamic University), Wirman (Singaperbangsa University)	2

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 35 topics, namely: analysis, bi rate, composite stock price index, conventional stock mutual fund, conventional stock mutual fund, ihsg, income mutual fund, independent variable, Indonesia composite index, Indonesia stock exchange, inflation, inflation rate, interest rate, Islamic mutual fund, issi, Jakarta Islamic index, nab, nav, nav equity fund, influence of inflation, purposive sampling method, rate, stock mutual funds, sharia mutual funds, research, research data, return, sbi, secondary data, sharia mutual fund, sharpe ratio, significant effect, stock mutual fund, stock selection, treynor ratio, variable.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 35 topics, namely: asset, balanced mutual funds, capital market, development, dissolution, expertise, financial service authority, form, implementation, increase, investment, investment fund, investment instrument, investment manager, investor, knowledge, lack, legal material, legal protection, liquidation, loss, mutual fund, mutual fund investor, mutual fund product, ojk, portfolio, position, principle, prospectus, risk, value, var, year.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 32 topics, namely: ability, according, cash flow, coefficient, expense ratio, fixed income fund, fund, fund age, fund size, Islamic mutual fund share, jci, jii, market timing, market timing ability, measurement, model, mutual fund performance, past performance, performance measurement, period, portfolio turnover, relationship, risk level, sbis, selectivity, sharia, significant influence, stock, stock exchange, stock selection skill, total assets, turnover ratio.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 26 topics, namely: benchmark, best performance, comparison, conventional equity fund, equity fund, index fund, Jensen, management, Sharpe method, Treynor method, money market mutual fund, observation period, financial services authority, performance, positive performance, quantitative approach, stock mutual funds sharia, research method, research period, risk, sharia equity fund, sharpe, sharpe method, treynor, treynor and Jensen, treynor method.
- Cluster 5. Purple consists of 17 topics, namely: analysis, Indonesian stock exchange, conventional mutual fund, difference, equity mutual fund, hypothesis, Indonesia stock exchange, market performance, mutual fund share, mutual, security selection, sharia mutual fund, sharpe index, significant difference, t test, treynor index, underperform.
- Cluster 6. The blue color consists of 14 topics, namely: capital protected fund, exchange rate, inflation, influence, money supply, multiple linear regression, net asset value, purposive sampling, sampling technique, sharia fund, spss, t count, t table, type.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 1 topic, namely: share.

Research Topic Mapping using Literature Study regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds

Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 522 Research topics regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds, namely:

- ALTERNATIVE INVESTMENT THROUGH MUTUAL FUNDS
- THE ROLE AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE INVESTMENT MANAGER IN MANAGING MUTUAL FUNDS
- WHAT, HOW AND IMPACT OF MUTUAL FUNDS

- Legal Position of Collective Investment Contract Mutual Fund Unit Holders
- Choose Mutual Funds with the Appropriate Rate of Return and Risk Level
- The Existence of Sharia Mutual Funds in the Perspective of Islamic Economic Law
- Performance Analysis of Nusantara Mutual Fund PT Bhakti Asset Management and Preparation of Theoretical Optimum Portfolio for the Period January - April 2005
- THE ROLE OF PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS AND FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING STANDARDS FOR MUTUAL FUND ACTIVITIES
- Performance Analysis of Stock Mutual Funds Using the Raw Return, Sharpe, Treynor, Jensen and Sortino Methods
- Ability to Select Shares and Market Timing of Equity Mutual Fund Investment Managers on the Indonesian Stock Exchange
- Persistent Performance of Equity Mutual Funds on the Indonesian Stock Exchange
- Performance Analysis of Mutual Funds Registered with Bapepam According to the Risk Adjusted Return Method
- REVIEW OF CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS AND SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- Comparison of Conventional Mutual Fund Performance with Conventional Index (LQ45)
- The Influence of Total Assets, Number of Securities, Portfolio Turnover, Operating Profit/Loss and Accountant's Opinion on Audit Delay in Mutual Fund Products in Indonesia
- MUTUAL FUNDS AS AN INVESTMENT ALTERNATIVE
- Juridical Review of Sharia Mutual Funds as an Investment Alternative for Investors
- Analysis of Stock Mutual Fund Performance Using the Sharpe and Jensen Method for the Period 2005 – 2009
- Performance Analysis of the 14 Best Equity Mutual Funds for the 2010 Period
- MEASUREMENT OF MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE USING ALPHA ($\bar{I} \pm$) CALCULATION RESULTS OF THE 'JENSEN INDEX' IN THE INDONESIAN CAPITAL MARKET
- COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS
- Assessment of the Performance of Equity Mutual Funds in Indonesia When the Market Rises and Falls in 2007 – 2009
- MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT WITH THE MUDHARABAH SYSTEM BY PT. BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI PEKALONGAN
- Evaluation of the Performance of Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia According to the Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Method and Comparison of Stock Mutual Fund Returns with LQ45 for the Period January 2009 – June 2010
- PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS BASED ON THE SHARPE METHOD, TREYNOR METHOD AND JENSEN METHOD
- FATHER DINHO'S FAMILY FINANCIAL PLANNING ON SAVINGS AND MUTUAL FUNDS

- Mr. Tonny's Family Financial Planning on Savings and Mutual Funds
- THE INFLUENCE OF MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES ON THE COMBINED STOCK PRICE INDEX AND NAV RETURN OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS (STUDY ON STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS REGISTERED WITH BAPEPAM PERIOD 2008-2012)
- COMPARISON OF INVESTMENT RESULTS IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE LUMP SUM AND DOLLAR COST AVERAGE METHODS: CASE STUDY OF THE PANIN DANA MAKSIMA MUTUAL FUND
- ANALYSIS OF MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT USING THE SHARPE METHOD AND TREYNOR METHOD (Study of Equity Mutual Funds for the 2011-2012 Period)
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MACRO VARIABLES ON DEMAND FOR STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA FOR THE PERIOD 2001 - 2011
- RESPONSIBILITY OF INVESTMENT MANAGERS REGARDING DEFECTS MADE AGAINST COLLECTIVE INVESTMENT CONTRACT MUTUAL FUND INVESTORS IN DENPASAR
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF ISLAMIC MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA UNTIL 2012
- Determination Analysis of Fixed Income Mutual Fund Performance in Indonesia for the 1999-2003 Period (Using the Jensen Model and Gudikunst Model)
- Comparison of the Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds with Conventional Mutual Funds
- Evaluation of the Performance of Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia Based on Stock Portfolio in 2010-2012
- SHARIA PERSPECTIVE ON DANAREKSA SYARIAH BERIMBANG MUTUAL FUND MANAGEMENT
- LONG TERM STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENTS IN INDONESIA BASED ON THE DECISION OF THE CHAIRMAN OF BAPEPAM - LK
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS WITH CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS TYPE OF SHARES IN THE PERIOD 2008 – 2012
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MARKET TIMING ABILITY, STOCK SELECTION SKILL, EXPENSE RATIO AND RISK LEVEL ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS (Study of KIK Type Stock Mutual Funds for the 2009-2013 Period)
- Comparative Analysis of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds with Conventional Stock Mutual Funds for the Period 2009–2012
- INTRODUCTION TO ISLAMIC MUTUAL FUNDS (INTRODUCTION OF ISLAMIC MUTUAL FUNDS)
- DIFFERENCES IN THE PERFORMANCE OF CONVENTIONAL AND SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- THE INFLUENCE OF MARKET SELECTIVITY CAPABILITY AND MARKET TIMING CAPABILITY OF INVESTMENT MANAGERS ON STOCK MUTUAL FUND PORTFOLIO RETURNS
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA

- Comparison of Equity Mutual Fund Investment Results Using Lump Sum and Dollar Cost Average Methods: Case Study of Panin Dana Maksima Mutual Funds
- LONG TERM STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENTS IN INDONESIA BASED ON THE DECISION OF THE CHAIRMAN OF BAPEPAM - LK
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS AND SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- COMPARISON OF VARIANCE COVARIANCE AND HISTORICAL SIMULATION METHODS TO MEASURE MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT RISK
- LONG TERM STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENTS IN INDONESIA BASED ON THE DECISION OF THE CHAIRMAN OF BAPEPAM - LK
- Evaluation of the Performance of Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia Based on Stock Portfolio in 2010-2012
- Performance Analysis and Optimal Portfolio Formation in Mutual Fund Products That Are Traded at PT. BANK MANDIRI (Persero) TBK
- ANALYSIS OF MEASUREMENT OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE USING THE RISK-ADJUSTED RETURN METHOD ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE PERIOD 2011-2013
- PERSISTENCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE
- External and Internal Factors That Influence Investment Returns on Mixed Mutual Fund Products in Indonesia
- DIFFERENCES IN THE PERFORMANCE OF CONVENTIONAL AND SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- Comparative Analysis of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds with Conventional Stock Mutual Funds for the 2009–2012 Period
- LONG TERM STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENTS IN INDONESIA BASED ON THE DECISION OF THE CHAIRMAN OF BAPEPAM - LK
- RESPONSIBILITY OF THE ISSUER AND CAPITAL MARKET SUPPORTING PROFESSIONALS FOR INCORRECT PROSPECTUS CONTENT IN MUTUAL FUND PUBLIC OFFERINGS
- Performance Analysis and Optimal Portfolio Formation in Mutual Fund Products That Are Traded at PT. BANK MANDIRI (Persero) TBK
- Sharia Mutual Funds
- ANALYSIS OF MEASUREMENT OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE USING THE RISK-ADJUSTED RETURN METHOD ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE PERIOD 2011-2013
- ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY (Empirical Study of Mutual Funds listed on the IDX)
- WINDOW DRESSING PRACTICES IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA, 2008-2012
- The Effect of Inflation, Rupiah Exchange Rate, BI Rate on Net Asset Value of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds
- ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP OF INSIDER OWNERSHIP WITH FUND RETURN, FUND TURN OVER, AND FUND TAX COST OF MUTUAL FUND STOCK PERIOD 2010-2013
- The Effect of Inflation, Rupiah Exchange Rate, BI Rate on Net Asset Value of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds

- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF FUND CASH FLOW, FUND SIZE, FUND LONGEVITY, EXPENSE RATIO AND TURNOVER RATIO ON MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE (Case Study: Fixed Income Mutual Funds for the 2011-2015 Period)
- MARKET TIMING, STOCK SELECTIVITY AND PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PRODUCTS IN INDONESIA
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF TOTAL ASSET, FUND AGE, EXPENSE RATIO AND PORTFOLIO TURNOVER ON MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE FOR THE 2012 - 2014 PERIOD
- THE INFLUENCE OF STOCK SELECTION ABILITY AND MARKET TIMING ABILITY ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS USING CONDITIONAL AND UNCONDITIONAL MODELS IN THE PERIOD 2009 - 2015
- CHARACTERISTICS OF MUTUAL FUNDS AND PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- THE EFFECT OF INFLATION, INTEREST RATES, MUTUAL FUND SIZE, AND MUTUAL FUND AGE ON MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE
- PERFORMANCE OF ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS: APPLICATION OF THE JENSEN MODEL
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND THE PERFORMANCE OF CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS
- PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS POST SUBPRIME MORTGAGE CRISIS
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF STOCK SELECTION SKILL AND MARKET TIMING ABILITY USING THE TREYNOR-MAZUY AND HENRIKSSON-MERTON METHOD ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS (Study of Stock Mutual Funds 2010-2014)
- STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS: ALTERNATIVE METHODS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT IN THE 5 INVESTMENT MANAGERS WITH THE LARGEST MANAGEMENT IN INDONESIA PERIOD 2006-2015
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIA (Empirical Study of Conventional Mutual Funds in Indonesia for the 2012-2014 Period)
- OPTIMIZATION OF VALUE AT RISK IN MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE HISTORICAL SIMULATION METHOD AND ITS APPLICATION USING MATLAB GUI
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND RETURNS WITH MARKET RETURNS BASED ON THE SHARPE METHOD, TREYNOR METHOD AND JENSEN METHOD
- The performance of sharia mutual funds and several factors that influence it: a study on the Indonesian capital market 2010-2013
- RESPONSIBILITIES OF INVESTMENT MANAGERS IN MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- OPTIMIZATION OF VALUE AT RISK MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE ROBUST EXPONENTIALLY WEIGHTED MOVING AVERAGE (ROBUST EWMA) METHOD WITH THE VOLATILITY UPDATING HULL AND WHITE PROCEDURE
- Sharia Mutual Funds in Islamic Law Perspective

- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF FUND AGE, MARKET TIMING ABILITY, STOCK SELECTION SKILL, PORTFOLIO TURNOVER AND FUND SIZE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE 2013 - 2015 PERIOD
- Investment Analysis for Tourism Potential Development in the Development of the Mekaki Bay Lombok Tourism Area Using the Tourism Rdpt Pattern (Limited Placement Mutual Fund - Tourism)
- Comparison of Sharia Fixed Income Mutual Funds and Sharia Stock Mutual Funds Based on Rate of Return in the Period January 2011 - December 2014
- Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Islamic and Conventional Equity Mutual Funds for the 2012-2015 Period
- Analysis of Stock Mutual Fund Performance using the Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Method
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS
- ANALYSIS OF MEASURING THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS LISTED ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE IN BULLISH AND BEARISH MARKET CONDITIONS
- The influence of market timing, mutual fund size and risk level on the performance of sharia stock mutual funds
- FORMATION OF THE OPTIMAL THREE LQ45 STOCK PORTFOLIO AND COMPARISON OF THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN OCTOBER 2016
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS, STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND MIXED MUTUAL FUNDS (STUDY ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE – BEI)
- CHARACTERISTICS OF MUTUAL FUNDS AND PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- The Influence of Investment Manager Performance and Asset Allocation Policy on the Performance of Equity Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- ANALYSIS OF OPTIMAL PORTFOLIO HEDGING OF THREE LQ-45 SHARES WITH ONE 5 STAR MUTUAL FUND (FIVE)
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF KIK STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS BASED ON RISK ADJUSTED PERFORMANCE METHOD FOR THE PERIOD OF 1 JANUARY 2007 – 31 DECEMBER 2009
- SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- The Influence of Size and Age on the Performance of Equity Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- Performance Analysis of Stock Mutual Funds Using the Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Method with IHSG and Lq45 (Stock Mutual Funds Registered with the OJK 2009-2013)
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND PROTECTED MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE METHOD AND THE TREYNOR METHOD
- Sharia Mutual Fund Investment in Indonesia
- Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Islamic and Conventional Equity Mutual Funds for the 2012-2015 Period
- Analysis of Stock Mutual Fund Performance using the Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Method

- Characteristics of Mutual Funds and Performance of Equity Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- Sharia Mutual Fund Investment in Indonesia
- Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Islamic and Conventional Equity Mutual Funds for the 2012-2015 Period
- Stock Selection and Timing Capabilities of Stock Mutual Fund Investment Managers in Indonesia
- The Influence of Inflation, IHSG, Size and Age on the Performance of Equity Mutual Funds for the 2012 - 2016 Period
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF STOCK SELECTION SKILL, MARKET TIMING ABILITY, TOTAL ASSET, AND EXPENSE RATIO ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SYARIAH MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA FOR THE 2013-2016 PERIOD
- COMPARISON OF THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND PROTECTED MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE METHOD (Study of Stock Mutual Funds and Protected Mutual Funds Registered with the Financial Services Authority 2015-2017)
- ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIA USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS (Study of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds Registered with the Financial Services Authority for the 2015 - 2017 Period)
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE METHOD (Study of Fixed and Mixed Income Mutual Funds for the 2015-2017 Period)
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF CONVENTIONAL STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS APPROACHES TO THE SHARPE METHOD AND TREYNOR MEASUREMENT
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA AND IN SAUDI ARABIA USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS (Study of Sharia Equity Mutual Funds Registered with the Financial Services Authority and Capital Market Authority for the 2014 - 2017 Period)
- COMPARISON OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS
- GUERRILLA STRATEGY IN RAISING PUBLIC AWARENESS OF INVESTMENT INSTRUMENTS IN SHARIA CAPITAL MARKET PRODUCTS PARTICULARLY SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT AS AN EVALUATION OF INVESTOR PORTFOLIO IN THE CAPITAL MARKET USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR, AND JENSEN MEASUREMENT METHODS
- ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE USING SHARPE, M SQUARE AND INFORMATION RATIO METHODS WITH LQ-45 INDEX AS BENCHMARK
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE AND TREYNOR METHOD (Study of Fixed Income Mutual Funds Registered with the Financial Services Authority for the 2015 - 2017 Period)
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE AND TREYNOR METHOD (Study of Sharia Mutual Funds

- Registered with the Financial Services Authority for the 2016 – 2018 Period)
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS USING SHARPE, TREYNOR, JENSEN, AND M2 METHODS (STUDY ON SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS REGISTERED WITH THE FINANCIAL SERVICES AUTHORITY)
 - STUDY OF THE HEALTH OF YUDHA BHAKTI BANK AS A FEASIBILITY FOR BANK PLACEMENT OF MUTUAL DEPOSITS AND SYAILENDRA MONEY MARKET FUNDS CASH FUNDS PT. SYAILENDRA CAPITAL
 - Performance of Stock Mutual Funds Using the Sharpe Method
 - Performance Analysis of Mutual Funds Registered with Bapepam According to the Risk Adjusted Return Method
 - FORECASTING MUTUAL FUND INCOME IN A YEAR USING SIMPLE LINEAR REGRESSION METHOD
 - MEASUREMENT OF MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE IN SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA FOR THE PERIOD 2008 – 2018
 - ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUND EFFICIENCY USING DATA ENVELOPMENT ANALYSIS (DEA) METHOD
 - Accounting Analysis for Corporate Liquidation in Prima Xi Tram Protected Mutual Funds
 - ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS (EQUITY FUNDS) USING THE TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHOD (Study of Stock Mutual Funds Registered with BAPEPAM 2011 – 2015)
 - THE INFLUENCE OF STOCK SELECTION SKILLS, MARKET TIMING ABILITY, TURNOVER RATIO AND CASH FLOW ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
 - Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Conventional and Sharia Mutual Funds in Crisis and Non-Crisis Periods
 - MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIA IS REVIEWED FROM STOCK SELECTION AND RISK LEVEL
 - LEGAL PROTECTION OF INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE MUTUAL FUND PARTICIPATION UNIT HOLDERS
 - Stock Selection and Market Timing Ability of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia
 - Accounting Analysis for Corporate Liquidation in Prima Xi Tram Protected Mutual Funds
 - PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS: COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN FIXED INCOME SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND THEIR BENCHMARKS FOR THE 2014-2017 PERIOD
 - Analysis of Stock Mutual Fund Performance Measurement as an Evaluation of Investor Portfolio in the Capital Market Using the Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen Measurement Method (Case Study on the Indonesian Stock Exchange 2013 – 2017)
 - Comparison of the Performance of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds and Conventional Stock Mutual Funds Based on the Sharpe and Treynor Methods
 - Performance of Stock Mutual Funds Using the Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Methods in the Period January 2014 to December 2015

- ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INVESTOR SENTIMENT AND STOCK MARKET RETURNS USING THE MUTUAL FUND FLOW APPROACH AND VECTOR AUTOREGRESSIVE (VAR) ANALYSIS
- Stock Selection and Market Timing Ability of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- The Influence of Systematic Risk, Market Timing, and Fund Size on the Performance of Sharia Fixed Income Mutual Funds in Indonesia (Period 2014-2018)
- PROTECTION OF MUTUAL FUND CUSTOMERS IN THE NEGLIGENCE OF FUND PLACEMENT BY INVESTMENT MANAGERS
- The Role of Exchange-Trade Funds (ETF) to Encourage the Growth of the Mutual Fund Industry in the Indonesian Capital Market
- THE EFFECT OF INFLATION, EXCHANGE, SBI, SBIS ON NET ASSETS VALUE (NAV): PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF MONEY MARKET SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, EXCHANGE EXCHANGE AND IHSG ON THE RETURN OF PT NIKKO SECURITIES INDONESIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE 2014-2017 PERIOD
- THE EFFECT OF INFLATION, JAKARTA ISLAMIC INDEX, SHARIA BANK PROFITS ON SHARIA MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT
- Analysis of Stock Selection and Risk Level on Stock Mutual Fund Performance
- Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds in the Indonesian Capital Market
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE WITH CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE
- ANALYSIS OF EXPENSE RATIO, FUND SIZE, RISK LEVEL AND TURNOVER PORTFOLIO ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS
- THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, RUPIAH EXCHANGE RATE, BI RATE ON NET ASSETS VALUE OF SHARIA PROTECTED MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE 2014-2018 PERIOD
- Analysis of the Efficiency of Sharia Mutual Funds using the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) Method
- PERFORMANCE OF MONEY MARKET MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE (IDX) – PERIOD 2013 – 2017
- Stock Selection and Market Timing Ability of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia (RETRACT)
- THE INFLUENCE OF THE CAPITAL ASSET PRICING MODEL (CAPM) METHOD ON DETERMINING STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT CHOICES (Study of Companies Included in Stock Mutual Funds for the 2016-2017 Period)
- COMPARISON OF MEAN AVERAGE PERCENTAGE ERROR IN FORECASTING MUTUAL FUND PRICE MOVEMENTS USING THE HOLT AND BROWN'S DOUBLE EXPONENTIAL SMOOTHING METHOD
- ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY OF SHARI'AH STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS INVESTED BY PT. GENERAL TAKAFUL INSURANCE FOR THE 2012-2014 PERIOD

- APPLICATION OF ARCH/GARCH TO FORECAST VOLATILITY OF SHARIA MIXED MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL MIXED MUTUAL FUNDS
- YOUNG INVESTORS' INTEREST IN INVESTING MUTUAL FUNDS IN BUKALAPAK
- Business Sustainability: Analysis of Market Timing and Stock Selection of Indonesian Stock Mutual Funds
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MIXED MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT MANAGERS IN INDONESIA FOR THE PERIOD 2006-2012
- LEGAL ASPECTS OF MUTUAL FUNDS COLLECTIVE INVESTMENT CONTRACTS AS TRUSTS
- Expense Ratio, Portfolio Turnover, and Stock Mutual Fund Returns
- FORMULATION OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AGAINST MUTUAL FUNDS THAT COMMIT UNLAWFUL ACTS ACCORDING TO POSITIVE LAW IN INDONESIA
- THE INFLUENCE OF EXCHANGE RATE, MONEY SUPPLY AND INFLATION ON NET ASSETS VALUE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA, 2015-2019
- Macroeconomic Factors That Influence the Net Asset Value of Sharia Equity Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- Mutual Fund Investment as an Investment Alternative for Beginner Investors
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS REGISTERED WITH THE FINANCIAL SERVICES AUTHORITY
- THE INFLUENCE OF SBI, INFLATION, IHSG AND MARKET UNSYSTEMATIC RISK ON THE NAV OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS
- THE INFLUENCE OF ASSET ALLOCATION POLICIES AND RISK LEVELS ON MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIA (PERIOD 2016-2018)
- THE INFLUENCE OF IHSG, EXCHANGE RATE, AND BI RATE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS (Study of Fixed Income Mutual Funds Registered with the Financial Services Authority for the 2015 – 2019 Period)
- Indonesian Stock Mutual Fund Performance Assessment Application using the Jensen Alpha Method Based on CAPM 4 Factors
- The Influence of Inflation, Interest Rates, Mutual Fund Size and Mutual Fund Age on Mutual Fund Performance in 2014-2018
- THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, IHSG AND RETURN RATE ON TOTAL NET ASSETS VALUE (NAV) OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- Analysis of Portfolio Performance and Capabilities of Sharia Mutual Fund Investment Managers in Indonesia
- Implementation of K-Means and Naïve Bayes Integration in Identifying Mutual Fund Risk Levels
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS USING SHARPE AND TREYNOR METHODS (CASE STUDY ON SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE 2015-2019 PERIOD)
- THE INFLUENCE OF EXCHANGE RATE AND INFLATION ON NET ASSETS VALUE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA, 2015-2019

- The Effect of Inflation, BI-7 Day Reverse Repo Rate, Exchange Rate, Money Supply and Composite Stock Price Index on Net Asset Value of Equity Mutual Funds
- Analysis of Performance Measurement of Stock Mutual Funds Using the Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen Methods on the Indonesian Stock Exchange
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING INDIVIDUAL INTEREST IN INVESTING MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE BIBIT APPLICATION (Case Study of Undergraduate Students Majoring in Accounting Class 2017-2020, Faculty of Economics and Business, Brawijaya University)
- PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- Legal Protection for Investors Holding Mutual Fund Participation Units Who Promise Fixed Returns
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF CONVENTIONAL STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN MUTUAL FUNDS REGISTERED WITH THE FINANCIAL SERVICES AUTHORITY
- THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, SIZE AND AGE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- The Influence of the Composite Stock Price Index, Macroeconomic Factors on the Performance of Stock Mutual Funds
- Legal Protection for Investors Regarding the Dissolution of Mutual Fund Legal Entities
- The Influence of Sharia Stocks, Sukuk, and Sharia Mutual Funds on Indonesia's Economic Growth with the Exchange Rate as a Moderating Variable in 2011-2020
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF INVESTOR PROTECTION FORMS BY INVESTMENT MANAGERS IN MANAGING MUTUAL FUNDS
- Determinants of Mixed Mutual Fund Performance Factors in Indonesia: Determinants of Mixed Mutual Fund Performance Factors in Indonesia
- Analysis of the Influence of Internal Factors and External Factors on the Performance of Sharia Equity Mutual Funds
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIA
- Comparative Analysis of the Performance of Conventional Stock Mutual Funds and Sharia Stock Mutual Funds in Mutual Funds Registered with the Financial Services Authority
- MAPPING INVESTOR PERCEPTIONS OF PUBLIC MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENTS USING THE MULTIDIMENSIONAL SCALING METHOD
- Performance of Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia During the Covid-19 Pandemic
- Legal Protection for Investors Regarding the Dissolution of Mutual Fund Legal Entities
- The influence of ISSI, JIBOR, JISDOR and JUB exchange rates on the NAB of Sharia Mutual Funds (Sucorinvest Sharia Equity Fund)
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS DURING THE PANDEMIC PERIOD
- ANALYSIS OF MEASUREMENT OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE IN INDONESIA USING THE JENSEN METHOD

- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS REGARDING LEGAL PROTECTION OF INVESTORS AGAINST LIQUIDATION OF MUTUAL FUND PRODUCT DISSOLUTION CARRIED OUT BY OJK REVIEWED FROM LAW NO. 8 OF 1995 CONCERNING CAPITAL MARKETS (Case study of PT Minna Padi Asset Management)
- The Influence of Tracking Error and Risk on the Performance of Sharia Index Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- The Influence of Compound Annual Growth Rate, Drawdown, Expense Ratio, and Total Assets Under Management on Decision Making to Invest in Mutual Funds
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE, JENSEN AND TREYNOR METHOD ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE
- THE INFLUENCE OF MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA, 2013-2020
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS USING THE SHARPE INDEX APPROACH TO FIXED INCOME SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE PERIOD 2016-2019
- The influence of sharia shares, sharia mutual funds and foreign investment on economic growth in Indonesia in 2011-2020
- Factors That Influence the Performance of Equity Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- The Influence of Macroeconomic Factors on Net Asset Value in Sharia Equity Mutual Funds
- Comparative Analysis: Impact of Macroeconomic Variables on Performance Between Islamic and Conventional Equity Mutual Funds at the Financial Services Authority
- DETERMINANTS OF MACROECONOMIC INDICATORS FOR SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA FOR THE 2014-2021 PERIOD
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MACROECONOMIC FACTORS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF PROTECTED MUTUAL FUNDS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC
- COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND NON-SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS DURING THE PANDEMIC
- Sharia Mutual Fund Performance Measurement is Based on Risk and Rate of Return
- The Influence of Stock Selection Skill, Market Timing Ability, and Fund Age on the Performance of Stock Mutual Funds with Fund Cash Flow as an Intervening Variable in Companies Registered with the Financial Services Authority for the 2016 - 2020 Period
- Analysis of Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesian Economy
- The Performance of Collective Investment Contracts of Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- INFLUENCE MANAGER'S INVESTMENT ATTITUDE ON ORGANIZATION ENVIRONMENT AND PORTFOLIO PERFORMANCE MUTUAL FUND SHARES (Study on Mutual Fund Management Company Mutual Fund Shares in Indonesia)

- Correlation Analysis between Jakarta Composite Index and LQ45 Index With Net Asset Value of Equity Mutual Fund and Balanced Mutual Fund
- The Evolution of the Trust System in the Mutual Fund Business in Indonesia (A Study Based on Islamic Law Perspective)
- The Application of Asset Allocation Strategy Using Panin Mutual Fund Products in 2005-2009 Period of Investment
- Value Effect in Indonesian Stock Returns: The Implications for the Equity Mutual Fund Industry
- Ambiguity towards Multiple Historical Performance Information Signals: Evidence from Indonesian Open-Ended Mutual Fund Investors
- Fund Manager Characteristics and The Social Performance of Conventional Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- RISK AND TURNOVER FROM INVESTING IN EQUITY MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE
- The Effect of Inflation, Interest Rate, and Indonesia Composite Index (ICI) to the Performances of Mutual Fund Return and Unit Link with Panel Data Regression Modeling
- Innovative Marketing Tools: A Case Study of IDFC Mutual Fund
- THE ROLE OF ISLAMIC CAPITAL MARKET FOR MICRO, SMALL, AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (MSMES) THROUGH SYNERGY OF MUTUAL FUND AND VENTURE CAPITAL INSTITUTION
- THE IMPACT OF MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE ON MUTUAL FUND MARKET VALUE WITH INTERNET FINANCIAL REPORTING (IFR) AS INTERVENING VARIABLE
- A Comparative Study of Mutual Fund Portfolio Performance in Indonesia
- Implementation of Syari'ah Economic Principles on the Management of Syari'ah Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- CUSTOMER PURCHASE INTENTION ON SHARIA MUTUAL FUND PRODUCTS: A TPB APPROACH
- Fund Age, BI Rate, Exchange Rate, and Jakarta Islamic Index on Net Asset Value in Islamic Equity Mutual Fund Indonesia
- Growth and Value Effect on Jakarta Islamic Index: Analysis towards Performance of Sharia Equity Mutual Fund
- The Optimization of Sharia Mutual Fund as an Investment Means to Promote Financial Inclusion in Indonesia
- THE INFLUENCES OF INTEREST RATE AND INFLATION ON SHARIA MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE
- Sharia Mutual Fund Performance, Foreign Ownership and Investment Ability
- Scale and Skill in Mutual Fund Management: Evidence from Norway
- The Effect of E-Marketing with the AISAS Model on Shariah Mutual Fund Investment Decisions at Bibit Mutual Fund Fintech
- The Islamic Economic Law Perspective on Sharia Mutual Fund Investment
- The Effect of Market Timing Ability and Fund Size on Mutual Fund Performance of Mutual Fund Companies in Indonesia
- Determinants of Islamic Mutual Fund Performance: A Comparative Study Between Indonesia and Malaysia

- THE ROLE OF EXCHANGE TRADED FUND TO DRIVE THE GROWTH OF THE MUTUAL FUND INDUSTRY IN THE CAPITAL MARKET ACCORDING TO A REVIEW OF ISLAMIC LAW
- LEARNING MODULES FOR TRAINING MUTUAL FUNDS TO INVESTORS
- INFLATION, BI 7 DAYS REPO RATE, AND JAKARTA COMPOSITE INDEX ON NET ASSET VALUE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUND
- Implementation of PSAK 71 In Indonesia: Mutual Fund Investment In Insurance Subsector Companies
- Why do investors choose a mutual fund?
- The Relationship Between Service Quality and Consumer Satisfaction Link: Does Perceived Value Have a Mediating Effect?: An Evidence from Mutual Fund Company in Jakarta
- Equity Mutual Fund Performance Analysis using Sharpe and Treynor Indices 2012-2013
- ANALYSIS OF MACRO ECONOMIC FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE SHARIA IN INDONESIA (2015-2019 PERIOD)
- DISRUPTION OF MACROECONOMICS ON ISLAMIC MUTUAL FUND
- THE EFFECT OF LEVERAGE AND ASSET PRICES ON MUTUAL FUND RISK IN MUTUAL FUND COMPANIES IN INDONESIA
- Determinants of Islamic Mutual Fund Performance: A Comparative Study Between Indonesia and Malaysia
- ASSET ALLOCATION POLICY ANALYSIS, SHARE SELECTION, AND LEVEL OF MUTUAL FUND RISK IN INDONESIA
- Juridical Review Concerning Civil Liability of Mutual Fund Investment Managers Against Lost Investors
- FACTORS INFLUENCING FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE
- The Relation of Fund Characteristics on Sharia Equity Mutual Funds Performance
- THE EFFECT OF EXPORT, ISLAMIC MUTUAL FUND, AND LABOR FORCE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN INDONESIA
- DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF THE PERFORMANCE OF OPEN MUTUAL FUNDS COLLECTIVE INVESTMENT CONTRACTS IN INDONESIA
- PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA FOR THE PERIOD OF APRIL-JULY 1997
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AGAINST CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS (MAWAR MUTUAL FUNDS) 1997 – 2001
- EVALUATION OF MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE BASED ON THE SHARPE, TREYNOR, JENSEN AND M2 METHODS?
- ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE AND RISK DIFFERENCES IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS, FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS, IHSG AND BOND INDEX USING THE SHARPE METHOD
- STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS
- Performance Analysis and Return Growth Potential of Stock Mutual Fund Portfolios and Mixed Mutual Funds
- MUTUAL FUND ACCOUNTING PRINCIPLES OF FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING STANDARDS (PSAK) NO. 49

- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF INTEREST RATES, INFLATION, CURRENCY EXCHANGES, IHSG AND MANAGED FUNDS ON STOCK MUTUAL FUND RETURNS
- INFLUENCE MANAGER'S INVESTMENT ATTITUDE ON ORGANIZATION ENVIRONMENT AND PORTFOLIO PERFORMANCE MUTUAL FUND SHARES (Study on Mutual Fund Management Company Mutual Fund Shares in Indonesia)
- SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND INDEX MUTUAL FUNDS IN ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF EFFICIENCY OF THE INDONESIAN CAPITAL MARKET
- Comparison of Risk and Return on Investment in Gold, Stocks and Mutual Funds in Determining Investment Decisions
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN 2009 IN INDONESIA
- MUTUAL FUND PROTECTION THROUGH GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNMENT (CASE STUDY OF GLOBAL BANK)
- ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE IN STOCK, BOND AND MUTUAL FUNDS BASED ON THE SHARPE METHOD IN INSURANCE COMPANY
- THE INFLUENCE OF INVESTMENT MANAGER ATTITUDES ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AND STOCK MUTUAL FUND PORTFOLIO PERFORMANCE (Study of Stock Mutual Fund Management Companies in Indonesia)
- ANALYSIS OF STOCK SELECTION AND MARKET TIMING CAPABILITY OF INVESTMENT MANAGERS IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- Mutual Fund Product Performance Assessment Using Jensen Alpha, Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, M2, and Information Ratio Calculation Methods
- MUTUAL FUND PROSPECTUS AS A PRINCIPLE OF SHARIA BUSINESS HONESTY
- Portfolio Performance Evaluation in Stock Mutual Funds
- ANALYSIS OF ASSET ALLOCATION POLICIES, INVESTMENT MANAGER PERFORMANCE AND RISK LEVELS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- IS THE PERFORMANCE AND RISKS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS BETTER THAN CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS?
- FATHER BUDI'S FAMILY FINANCIAL PLANNING ON MUTUAL FUND INSTRUMENTS
- FATHER MIKE'S FINANCIAL PLANNING FOR INSURANCE, SAVINGS AND MUTUAL FUNDS
- Testing the Consistency of Stock Mutual Fund Performance on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2008-2012 Period
- Mr
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RISK AND RATE OF RETURN OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS
- MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT ANALYSIS AS AN INVESTMENT ALTERNATIVE IN THE FUTURE
- CHARACTERISTICS OF MUTUAL FUNDS AND THEIR REGULATION IN CAPITAL MARKETS IN INDONESIA

- Comparative Analysis of Dinar Investment and Sharia Money Market Mutual Fund Investment
- THE ROLE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INCREASING INVESTMENT IN INDONESIA
- MEASUREMENT OF STOCK SELECTION AND TIME DETERMINATION USING THE TREYNOR-MAZUY MODEL IN SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF INDONESIAN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE PERIOD 2007 – 2011
- BEHAVIOR OF INVESTORS IN SHARES, MUTUAL FUNDS AND DEPOSITS: A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY
- ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENTS IN MUTUAL FUND INSTRUMENTS IN PENSION FUNDS (Study of the East Kalimantan Pupuk Pension Fund 2009-2012)
- DEVELOPMENT AND OBSTACLES OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA: A THEORETICAL STUDY
- THE INFLUENCE OF MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE AND RISK ON THE NUMBER OF ASSET UNDER MANAGEMENT AND PARTICIPATION UNITS
- DESCRIPTIVE STUDY OF STOCK, MUTUAL FUND AND DEPOSIT INVESTOR BEHAVIOR
- MECHANISM AND DEVELOPMENT OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- THE INFLUENCE OF THE COMBINED STOCK PRICE INDEX (IHSG), SBI INTEREST RATES, AND EXCHANGE RATE ON MUTUAL FUND PARTICIPATION UNITS
- Persistence and Consistency of Mutual Fund Performance in Indonesia
- BASIC CONCEPTS OF MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT
- THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, INTEREST RATES ON BANK INDONESIA CERTIFICATES & COMBINE STOCK PRICE INDEX ON THE RATE OF RETURN ON MUTUAL STOCK FUNDS (Study on the Indonesian Stock Exchange for the 2011 - 2013 Period)
- ANALYSIS OF BANK RESPONSIBILITY TOWARDS CUSTOMERS IN MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT PRODUCTS
- ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS (EQUITY FUNDS) USING THE SHARPE AND TREYNOR METHOD
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF STOCK SELECTION SKILL, MARKET TIMING ABILITY, FUND LONGEVITY, FUND CASH FLOW AND FUND SIZE ON MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE (Case Study: Stock Mutual Funds 2010-2014 Period)
- ANALYSIS OF MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF MIXED MUTUAL FUNDS
- FACTORS AFFECTING THE LEVEL OF RISK IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS
- Factors that Influence Investment in Mutual Funds
- INSURANCE IN STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE FORM OF AN OPEN COLLECTIVE INVESTMENT CONTRACT
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK AND FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE AND TREYNOR METHOD ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE

- TURNOVER AND NET ASSET PORTFOLIO WITH MARKET RETURN AS A MODERATING VARIABLE, EXPENSE RATIO, CASH AND SUBSCRIPTION FEE ON MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE IN THE 2009 - 2012 PERIOD
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, SBI INTEREST RATES, AND EXCHANGES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA (TIME PERIOD 2010-2014)
- The Effect of Interest Rates and Inflation on the Increase in Net Asset Value of Equity Mutual Funds
- LONG TERM SIMULTANEOUS BETWEEN STOCK PRICE INDEX FLUCTUATIONS, INFLATION RATE, INTEREST RATES AND IDR/USD EXCHANGE ON MUTUAL FUND SHARES RETURNS IN INDONESIA
- ANALYSIS OF MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENTS AND SOE PROFITS ON SOE STOCK PRICES ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE
- ANALYSIS OF MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF MIXED MUTUAL FUNDS
- Analysis of Sharia Mutual Fund Investment Portfolio Management in View of Investment Strategy Based on Investment Risk and Performance Measurement
- MUDHARIB MANAGERIAL CAPABILITY MODEL AS A BASIS FOR INVESTMENT IN SYARIAH MUTUAL FUNDS
- FAMILY FINANCIAL PLANNING THROUGH OPTIMIZING THE COMPOSITION OF INVESTMENTS IN SAVINGS, INSURANCE AND MUTUAL FUNDS BASED ON PRIORITY GOALS
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF CASH FLOW, FUND SIZE, FAMILY SIZE, EXPENSE RATIO, STOCK SELECTION ABILITY AND LOAD FEE ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE 2012-2014 PERIOD
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE INDONESIAN CAPITAL MARKET
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS (Study of Mutual Funds Registered with the Financial Services Authority for the 2012-2016 Period)
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF CONVENTIONAL STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE METHOD
- Comparison of the Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds and Conventional Mutual Funds Based on Risk and Return Levels
- Comparison of the Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds in Indonesia Using the SHARPE Method (Case Study of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds, Fixed Income Sharia Mutual Funds and Mixed Sharia Mutual Funds for the 2012-2014 period)
- COMPARISON OF THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS (ON STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS AND FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS LISTED ON THE BEI FOR THE 2010-2014 PERIOD)
- composite stock price index (ihsg) and jakarta interbank offered rate (jibor); performance of mixed mutual funds
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- UNDERSTANDING SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS: SHARIA BASED FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS

- ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE CONCEPT OF NET ASSETS VALUE (NAV)
- ANALYSIS OF THE DIFFERENTIAL ROOTS OF CONVENTIONAL AND SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- Analysis of the influence of Expense Ratio, Turnover Ratio, Mutual Fund Size and Cash Flow on mutual fund performance using the Sharpe method for the 2007-2011 period
- Analysis of the Root Differences between Conventional and Sharia Mutual Funds
- Analysis of Optimum Portfolio Risk Value in Mixed Mutual Funds Using the EWMA Approach
- ANALYSIS OF MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT PERFORMANCE IN PHILLIP SECURITIES MANADO USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS
- SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS VS CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS: GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT ANALYSIS 2010 – 2016
- The Influence of Investment Manager Performance on Sharia Equity Mutual Fund Returns in Indonesia (Period 2011-2015)
- Factors Affecting the Net Asset Value of Manulife Syariah Mutual Funds in the Amanah Sector
- Comparison of the Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds and the JII Market Using the Treynor Method (Case Study of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds, Fixed Income Sharia Mutual Funds and Mixed Income Sharia Mutual Funds for the 2011-2015 Period)
- The Influence of Macroeconomic Variables on the Net Asset Value (NAV) of Sharia Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- EVALUATION OF THE ABILITY OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT MANAGERS BASED ON MARKET TIMING AND STOCK SELECTION SKILL
- THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, EXCHANGE AND BI RATE ON NET ASSETS VALUE (NAV) OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA (PERIOD 2010-2016)
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS WITH CONVENTIONAL STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS (Mutual Funds registered with the OJK in 2013-2015)
- Analysis of Securities Selection Skill and Market Timing Ability on the Performance of Sharia Mixed Mutual Funds on the Indonesian Stock Exchange
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS WITH CONVENTIONAL STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- UNDERSTANDING SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS: SHARIA BASED FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS
- THE INFLUENCE OF TOTAL ASSETS, EXPENSE RATIO AND PORTFOLIO TURNOVER ON THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- Performance of Fixed Income Mutual Funds Using the Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen Methods

- Mutual Fund Operational Costs as an Intervening Influence of Mutual Fund Characteristics on the Performance of Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- Analysis of Factors That Influence Beginner Investors in Investing in Mutual Funds
- ANALYSIS OF RISK AND RETURN OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS COMPARED TO RANDOM STOCK PORTFOLIO
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA IN SEPTEMBER 2005 - AUGUST 2006
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MUTUAL FUND RETURNS WITH MARKET RETURNS AND RATING BASED ON THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MUTUAL FUND RETURNS BASED ON THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN METHODS
- Analysis of the Influence of the Rupiah Exchange Rate and Bank Indonesia Interest Rates on the Net Asset Value of Sharia Mutual Funds for the 2013-2015 Period
- ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE USING THE SHARPE AND TREYNOR METHOD (STUDY ON STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS REGISTERED WITH THE FINANCIAL SERVICES AUTHORITY 2014-2016)
- Comparative Analysis of Mutual Fund Returns Based on the Sharpe, Treynor and Jensen Methods
- Growth of Sharia Mutual Fund Institutions in Indonesia
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE TREYNOR AND BLACK MODEL METHOD
- The Influence of Inflation, Rupiah Exchange Rate, Amount of Money in circulation and the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) on the Net Asset Value of Sharia Mutual Funds
- THE INFLUENCE OF INFLATION, EXCHANGE AND BI RATE ON NET ASSETS VALUE (NAV) OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA (PERIOD 2010-2016)
- EVALUATION OF THE ABILITY OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT MANAGERS BASED ON MARKET TIMING AND STOCK SELECTION SKILL
- Analysis of the Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds (Share, Mixed and Fixed Income Categories) for the 2012-2017 Period
- COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE USING SHARPE AND TREYNOR METHOD ON STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS
- Stock Selection and Trading Times in Sharia Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- COMPARISON OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE WITH MARKET PERFORMANCE (ISSI) ON THE STOCK EXCHANGE
- MULTI AKAD MUAMALAH IN SYARI MUTUAL FUNDS ' AH
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA FOR THE 2014-2016 PERIOD
- Mutual Funds and Market Efficiency Assessment
- EVALUATION OF MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE AND INTEREST RATE POLICY: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA

- LEGAL PROTECTION OF INVESTORS IN ONLINE MUTUAL FUNDS
- Investing in Sharia Mutual Funds; A Critical Review
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA PROTECTED MUTUAL FUNDS USING THE SHARPE, TREYNOR AND JENSEN INDEX (PERIOD 2013-2016)
- DETERMINATION OF INVESTMENT BASED ON THE LEVEL OF RISK IN SHARIA STOCK, SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND GOLD PERIOD 2011-2015
- COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND NON-SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA BASED ON RETURN, RISK AND COEFFICIENT OF VARIATION
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MACROECONOMIC FACTORS ON THE NET ASSETS VALUE (NAV) OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE PERIOD OF JANUARY 2015 – JUNE 2017
- MEASURING THE PERFORMANCE OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS ON COMMODITY PRICES USING JENSEN'S ALPHA AND CAPM MEASURES
- PANEL DATA ANALYSIS ON STOCK MUTUAL FUND PERFORMANCE
- COMPARISON OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS WITH CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE WORLD OF BANKING
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES AND MUTUAL FUNDS ON THE SHARIA STOCK INDEX ON THE JAKARTA ISLAMIC INDEX (JII)
- THE INFLUENCE OF MACROECONOMIC FACTORS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF FIXED INCOME MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE 2015-2017 PERIOD
- Comparative Study of the Performance of Conventional and Sharia Equity Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- COMPARISON OF STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS OF NATIONAL AND FOREIGN INVESTMENT COMPANIES IN INDONESIA SEEN FROM PERFORMANCE, MARKET TIMING AND STOCK SELECTION
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE INDONESIAN CAPITAL MARKET USING THE SHARPE METHOD
- Investment Manager Defaults Against Mutual Fund Investors
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- LEGAL ASPECTS OF MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE FORM OF COLLECTIVE INVESTMENT CONTRACTS IN POSITIVE LAW IN INDONESIA
- MULTI AKAD MUAMALAH IN SYARIAH MUTUAL FUNDS
- Stock Selection and Trading Times in Sharia Stock Mutual Funds in Indonesia
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTEREST RATES, INFLATION RATE, COMBINED STOCK PRICE INDEX, AND GROWTH IN THE AMOUNT OF MONEY SUPPLY ON THE RATE OF RETURN ON MUTUAL STOCK FUNDS IN 2014-2017
- INTERNAL FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA FOR THE PERIOD 2014-2017)
- Socialization of the Introduction of Mutual Funds as an Investment Vehicle for Housewives
- Mutual fund rating prediction based on a decision tree algorithm in a mutual fund information system

- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS USING SHARPE, TREYNOR, JENSEN, M² AND TT METHODS
- Increasing the Value of Sharia Investments in Mutual Funds Using the Treynor-Mazuy Model Versus the Henriksson-Merton Model
- FACTORS THAT AFFECT CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN AUTOINVEST MUTUAL FUND CONSUMERS AT JAKARTA COMMONWEALTH BANK
- The Influence of Sharia Shares, Sukuk and Sharia Mutual Funds on Indonesia's Economic Growth (2012 - 2017)
- POLITICAL LEGAL FUNCTION OF BANK AS MUTUAL FUND AGENT IN CAPITAL MARKETS
- Optimal Mutual Fund Portfolio for Bluechip Shares in Bearish and Bullish Stock Market Conditions
- PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT MANAGERS IN INDONESIA
- The Influence of Money Supply and Economic Growth on the Performance of Stock Mutual Funds
- FACTORS - FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN AUTOINVEST MUTUAL FUND CONSUMERS AT JAKARTA COMMONWEALTH BANK
- TRAINING INTRODUCTION TO MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENT FOR STUDENTS OF ARIYA METTA VOCATIONAL SCHOOL
- DEVELOPMENT OF ISLAMIC ENTREPRENEURSHIP THROUGH SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- MEASUREMENT METHOD OF INFORMATION RATIO, SORTINO RATIO AND ROY SAFETY FIRST RATIO ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS FOR THE 2015-2017 PERIOD
- SHARIA MUTUAL FUND PORTFOLIO PERFORMANCE ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE 2013-2017
- COMPARISON OF RETURNS AND RISKS OF SHARIAH MUTUAL FUNDS WITH CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON MANAGED FUNDS
- REGULATION OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF POSITIVE LAW IN INDONESIA
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- PERFORMANCE STABILITY OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN FACING MACROECONOMIC SHUTTLE
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA USING THE SHARPE METHOD (Case Study of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds and Mixed Sharia Mutual Funds 2015-2016)
- Islamic Entrepreneurship Development Through Sharia Mutual Funds
- PROSPECTUS OF MUTUAL FUNDS AS SHARIA BUSINESS PRINCIPLES
- Performance of Stock Mutual Funds on the Bareksa Site
- Analysis of the Performance of Sharia Stock Mutual Funds in the Indonesian Capital Market Using the Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen Methods for the 2017-2018 Period
- Improving the Performance of Multi-Objective NSGA-II with Adaptive Mutation Operators in the Case of Stock Mutual Fund Portfolios
- Comparison of the Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds with Conventional Mutual Funds

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- Performance of Stock Mutual Funds on the Bareksa Site
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- POLITICAL LEGAL FUNCTION OF BANK AS MUTUAL FUND AGENT IN CAPITAL MARKETS
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- DETERMINANTS OF PERFORMANCE OF SHARIA STOCK MUTUAL FUNDS
- SHARIA MUTUAL FUND INVESTMENTS IN INDONESIA
- MEASURING THE BENEFITS OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS FROM A MAQASHID SHARIAH PERSPECTIVE
- Review of Islamic Law on Sharia Mutual Fund Investments
- Measuring the Level of Determination of Macroeconomic Variables on the Performance of Sharia Mutual Funds Using the Error Correction Model
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- The Influence of Macro Variables on the Net Asset Value (NAV) of Sharia Equity Mutual Funds
- Analysis of the Influence of Market Selectivity Timing Capability and the Effect of Fund Flow Dilution on Stock Mutual Fund Returns
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF INVESTORS IN INVESTMENTS THROUGH SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- INVESTMENT IN SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS IN INDONESIA
- IMPLEMENTATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS
- ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SHARIA MUTUAL FUNDS AND CONVENTIONAL MUTUAL FUNDS
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- MUTUAL FUNDS IN SYARIAH PERSPECTIVE
- The Influence of Macroeconomic Variables on the Growth Rate of Sharia Mutual Funds for the 2015 – 2019 Period
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- LEGAL PROTECTION OF MUTUAL FUND INVESTORS AGAINST INVESTMENT MANAGERS FAILING TO PAY IN COLLECTIVE INVESTMENT CONTRACTS
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Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 522 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Islamic and Conventional Mutual Funds.

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